

Article

Towards an Evolutionary Economic Theory

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Abstract: *Today, the neoclassic economic theory still dominates the economic analysis, prediction, and even public economic policy, encouraged, unfortunately, by the career criteria in science and education fields. In such a context, the objectives of the paper are: (1) to systematize the findings related to the unrealism and theoretical and methodological mistakes of the economic neoclassic model; (2) to argue about the desirability, reliability, realism, and efficaciousness of an evolutionary model of the economy (and of Economics); (3) to draw the basic lines which an evolutionary economic theory could be edified on, starting from both the statu quo in the matter and the logical examination of the question. The approach of research is a mix between logical and historical (but not empirical) views regarding the evolutionary economic model/theory. The main results are: (a) arguing on the possibility of crystalizing the basic concepts of an evolutionary economic model; (b) making proposals for the evolutionary economic mechanism (in its abstract understanding – as cybernetic system of order 3); (c) warning on the risks of a tale quale taking over of the evolutionary concepts from Biology; (d) identifying the principles to be followed in building up of an evolutionary economic theory.*

Keywords: *neoclassic economic model; evolutive mechanism; economic chreode; smart economy.*

1. Introduction

1.1. A bird's eye view

The economic theory is today under the pressure of reconsidering its epistemological framework, on the one hand, and, of the necessity to become more realistic (especially regarding the „true” predictions provided), on the other hand. The economic theory has begun under the political economy auspices (Smith, Cannan, 1997) but, further, it has been adjudicated by the neoclassical economic model (in fact, a mathematical formalization of the economic behaviour). This historical path has conferred to economic theory some elegance from a logical perspective, without doubt, but with an unacceptable price: the departure from the realism in the economic actual behaviour modelling.

The success of evolutionary theory in Biology (which had large suggestions for the social field, besides), as well as the entropy theory (discovered in Thermodynamics but quickly emigrated into other fields, including Economics (Georgescu-Roegen, 1971) and, more generally, the society (Dinga *et al.*, 2020). A very good binder between neoclassical Economics and evolutionary Economics was institutionalism¹ (North, 1990). Other contributions, from as different as possible perspectives, also press on the economic theory to change its epistemology, methodology, and even object–topology (Spencer-Brown, 1972), fractality and fractal dimension (Peters, 1994), structuralism, etc. All the mentioned signals that something must be made with the economic theory, to get it out of the neoclassicism imperium. To be

mentioned, for example, some (regional) contributions in edifying evolutionary Economics have been already provided: at the microeconomic level, based on the concept of routine as phenotype (Nelson, Winter, 1985), at the macroeconomic level, based on the concept of adaptation (Lo, 2017), and evolution (Dowling, 2005).

1.2. About the paper

The *objectives* of the paper are: (1) to systematize the findings related to the unrealism and theoretical and methodological mistakes of the economic neoclassic model; (2) to argue about the desirability, reliability, realism, and efficaciousness of an evolutionary model of the economy (and of Economics); (3) to draw the basic lines which an evolutionary economic theory could be edified on, starting from both the *statu quo* in the matter and the logical examination of the question.

The objectives are got using rather a *logical* (and, partially, historical) than an empirical methodological *approach*, to ensure that the allegations keep the highest generality possible.

The research is organized in three sections: (i) the *statu quo* of Economics; (ii) the evolutionary paradigm of Economics; (iii) epistemological and methodological consequences of evolutionary paradigm of Economics.

2. The *statu quo* of Economics

For a long time, economics realized that the neoclassical aegis under which it continues to stay and work (unfortunately, still encouraged by the Nobel Committee) is a blocked road. Although the mathematical elegance of the neoclassical models is very attractive (but not always the aesthetics is a criterion of the truth!), their realism is almost nonexistent. The death of the neoclassical economic theory has been many times declared, and the critics of it have spread monuments of logic and ingenuity, but the funeral has not yet taken place.

Of course, the flagrant departure of the neoclassic economic theory/model from the real world received, over time, many pertinent alternatives, more or less taken to the end, more or less epistemologically grounded – Keynesian theory (with its inherent prefixes *neo* and/or *post*), institutionalism, neo-Marxism, to remember the loudest labels – as well as essays to revitalize the neoclassicism itself – see the Neo-liberalism.

In my opinion, except the lane of neo-classicism, the other directions to rebuild the economic theory are regional, i.e., are focused on a side or other which are considered the core of the epistemology and methodology of Economics, without trying to edify general theory (*Nota bene*: even Keynesian theory is rather a macroeconomic one, although is called „general theory”, and the Samuelsonian neoclassical synthesis still contain an imbalance between microeconomics and macroeconomics in favour of macroeconomics).

The representative character of neoclassicism in the economic theory can be found especially in the financial theory – see, for example, Fama’s Efficient Market Hypothesis (elaborated also under Samuelson’s shadow).

Generally, the neoclassical model of economic theory, can be synthetized as follows:

- I. The classical economic science still remains the prisoner of the mechanistic paradigm
 - a. the economic process is considered to be a mechanistic process:
 - a fully causal process;
 - the causality of the economic process is eutaxiological (the observable order has an efficientⁱⁱ cause); it is noteworthy that in the teleological causality, the observable order has a purpose (final cause);

- the time and space which „locate” the economic process are taken to be absolute (independent of the economic process itselfⁱⁱⁱ);
 - the economic subject is considered a sui-generis machinery to optimise decisions; it is located exogenously in relation to the economic process;
 - the values, irrationality, the lack of direct interest, intuition, are not considered to be valid variables of the economic process;
 - the nonlinearities, bifurcations, single points, are not considered attributes of the classical economic process;
- b. therefore, the classical modelling of the economic process has the following attributes:
- it relies on the hypothesis of optimality (extremisation of an objective-function in a system of given restrictions);
 - it relies on dynamic equations (even if the dynamic characteristic rather relaxes by the introduction of the statistic-type random variables);
 - it relies on the exogenous nature of the human subject (as decision-maker and participant in the economic process), which ignores the Oedipus effect (the Oedipus effect is the one that changes the initial conditions^{iv});
 - it relies on the invariability of the initial (or final, according to situation) conditions of the economic process.
- II. The classical economic science still is prisoner of the eutaxiological causality
- c. the Hayekian economic order (more precisely, the catalactic order) is an eutaxiologically-generated order, which:
- relies on four essential methodological invariances:
 - invariance of the law in relation with the initial conditions (universality);
 - invariance of the law in relation with the time arrow (reversibility);
 - invariance of the law in relation with the quantitative accumulations (proportionality);
 - invariance of the law in relation with the final causes (impersonality or non-teleologicity);
 - rejects the idea according to which the efficient causes of the economic process are effects of the final causes;
 - considers the anthropic principle as an a posteriori principle:
 - therefore, the future cannot be constructed in a normative manner, it can only be forecast causally;
 - the modelling of the economic process only offers the possibility for an exogenous choice, from a list of morphologically generated options, with no possibility of intervention (the possible world are already given^v);
- d. man (as individual and/or as society) is located outside the economic process (be it a real process, a desirable projection or ex post evaluation):
- the implicit hypothesis of the eutaxiological causality is conceptually non-realistic:
 - man influences the economic process from the inside (the Oedipus effect – i.e. the variation of the initial conditions), introducing Heisenberg-type imprecisions;
 - prediction in the economic process depends on three factors: 1) initial conditions; 2) law of movement; 3) permanent evaluation of the contextual desirability (the eutaxiological causality neglects the third factor);

- ignoring the Oedipus effect is equivalent with rejecting the teleology of the economic process (but the economic process is an artefact, therefore teleological by nature);
 - this implicit hypothesis of the eutaxiological causality is methodologically disturbing:
 - in the mathematical functions describing the economic process, man is only considered among the independent variable for the species of the “production factor”.
- III. The dominant economic science (positivist) is the victim of an epistemological imperialism exerted by the Newtonian mechanics
- e. the mechanistic paradigm has been assumed by many economists and even by philosophers (such as Kant);
 - f. the most notable “improvement” was achieved by the neoclassicism;
 - g. this state of fact bestows upon the dominant economic science a “tragic character” in the play of the human knowledge and practice (meaning that it is doomed for „epistemological disappearance”);
 - h. lacking genuinity, the economic science is yet to have its own epistemology, parasiting other epistemologies, particularly that of the classical physics (also see the “synthesis” termed econophysics, an attempt to resuscitate a wrong epistemology).
- IV. The dominant (positivist) economic science is the author of an epistemological imperialism exerted on the other social sciences (politology, sociology, psychology, law, anthropology, etc.)
- i. see, particularly, the „work” of Gary Becker (Nobel Prize laureate for economy?), and of uncounted and relentless „quantifiers” in this field;
 - j. the tale quale methodological transfer from economy to non-economic social sciences may be characterized as “epistemological crime”;
 - k. or, rewording a famous phrase (Talleyrand), it is more than a crime, it is a mistake;
 - l. however, this imperialism is improper, because the economic science doesn’t transfer its genuine epistemological or methodological precepts, rather those received from the Newtonian mechanics (it is merely a transmission channel).

3. The evolutionary paradigm of Economics

The evolutionary paradigm of economics (and of the economic activity or economic system as well) is a „natural” tendency of reflections in the economic field, considering the unrealism and (to an extent) the anti-humanism of the neoclassical economic theory.

In my opinion, there are three perspectives from which the conditions to pass to elaboration an evolutionary theory/model of Economics are rope: (a) theoretical perspective; (b) methodological perspective; (c) praxiological perspective.

3.1. The theoretical perspective

(1) ($T - E$) there is an *entanglement* between rationality model and cultural conditioning

The impact: economic and financial entities are always *artifacts*, subject to teleology.

(2) ($T - R$) the bounded rationality (Simon) is also a *fallible* rationality

The impact: predicative reasoning/judgment is not exempt at all from errors.

(3) ($T - A$) *autopoiesis* (Maturana&Varela) principle gives to economic/social processes a new base for explanations (i.e., for causal descriptions)

The impact: constitutes the basic methodological anchor for (self)-replication of systems.

(4) ($T - B$) *behaviourism* introduces the (general) *conditioning* from the side of the societal environment (by putting together cognition, emotion, and teleology) (Skinner)

The impact: the psychology, anthropology and ecology add themselves to the economic ground of decision and action (either as act or as abstention).

- (5) ($T - L$) the *entropy law* as well as the *constructal law* (Bejan) aspire at the statute of the most general principles of causality in the social field

The impact: the possibilities (and suggestions) to build up explanatory *meta-systems* as way of knowledge increase towards equalizing that of the *categorial* knowledge.

- (6) ($T - I$) *institutionalism*, that provides a logic of behaviour within a normative framework

The impact: builds up the evolutionism from the society perspective, that must be completed with the evolutionism from the (biological) individual perspective.

3.2. The methodological perspective

- (1) ($M - N$) *network analysis* has overcome (as relevance, veracity, and generality) the differential equations

The impact: the subject is really re-introduced inside the process analysed.

- (2) ($M - H$) *hypercycle* (Eigen & Schuster) has become the causal mechanism *par excellence*, in natural, social, and cultural fields (*Nota bene*: including a kind of... *causa sui*)

The impact: a functional causality is added to the (standard) structural causality .

- (3) ($M - F$) *fractality* and fractal dimension of economic/social processes (Peters, 1994) and phenomena seems to be an inherent principle in the growth and development matter (a topology of time horizons)

The impact: an analytical new structural grid becomes methodologically available, so to regain the knowledge vocation of the structuralism (as developed in linguistic and anthropology).

- (4) ($M - A$) *abduction* replaces both the pure deduction and the pure induction

The impact: deduction's certainty and induction's uncertainty are replaced by the abduction's plausibility.

- (5) ($M - D$) *deterministic chaotism* of the systems which are sensitive to the initial conditions

The impact: allows both the renouncing to the probabilities (either objective or subjective) and the factual testing of the hypotheses.

- (6) ($M - T$) *topological approach* (Spencer-Brown, 1972) of the economic/financial behaviour (both in space and time) aimed at capturing the natural and cultural shapers of the individual's behaviour towards reproducibility (i.e., the global evolutive behaviour)

The impact: allows the renouncing to the simple kinematics description provided by differential equations and replacing them with a topological interaction which is much more adequate to the economic process (where we have free will besides the pure necessity).

3.3. The praxiological perspective

- (1) ($P - A$) growing *awareness* of the necessity to *replace* the *optimality* praxiological/actional paradigm with the *sustainability* praxiological/actional paradigm

The impact: functional mixes between the pairs: a) short-term – long-term; b) current generation – next generation; c) nature – culture; d) nurture – ethics.

- (2) ($P - L$) *prevalence of Lamarckism* over the Darwinism in the economic/social phenomenology

The impact: the purpose (the intention) dominates on the finality (the inherence).

- (3) ($P - F$) *freedom and democracy* (as ideals of the societal system) imply harmonization between the individual and the state

The impact: the only desirable and reliable social/political mechanism becomes the Ordoliberalism.

(4) ($P - R$) elaborated (regional) *proposals on the evolutionary path* in economic phenomenology (Nelson, Winter, 1985; Dowling, 2005; Lo, 2017; Dinga et al., 2020)

The impact: suggestions to pass from particular cases of evolutionism to more general ones

(5) ($P - S$) *sustainability paradigm*, aimed at replacing the optimality one, based on self-replicability and circularity between inputs and outputs/outcomes

The impact: integrating of the subject in (economic/financial) systems or order 3 (*Nota bene*: systems of order 1: the subject is outside the system; systems of order 2: the subject is inside the system; systems of order 3: systems are created by the subject him/herself).

(6) ($P - A$) *artificial intelligence* exponentially increases the possibility and the range of *long-term simulations* on the economic and financial

The impact: the evolutionary path of economic/financial processes becomes obvious and, perhaps, inevitable from theoretical and methodological perspectives.

4. Some epistemological consequences of evolutionary paradigm of Economics

Evolutionarily modelling of the economic (general) process, with inherent particularities in different economic „regions”, brings some important changes in the economic epistemology. In my opinion, the most relevant five of them are as follows:

Regarding the economic truth

Since, in the social (including economic) field, we have to do, generally, with artifacts, the purpose of the economic activity is, also, an (intellectual) artifact. Consequently, the outcome of an economic action is a desire, i.e., a teleological entity. This means that the objectivity of that outcome is altered by the necessary subjectivity of both prediction of the outcome and the measurement of it. In a word, the economic truth is a praxiological truth, not (necessarily) an objective one. A problem rising here is that of the inter-subjective relevance of the praxiological truth^{vi}. My opinion resides in the following:

- in the economic field, the most actions are common to many individuals (i.e., are, in fact, activities), which implies to formulate common purposes for those actions; so, generally, there is a consensus regarding the results of such actions, at least within the individuals directly involved;
- in the democratic societies, the macroeconomic purposes are established by the legislative power (Parliament) which is presupposed to objectify the needs (or purposes) of the entire society;
- consequently, I think the praxiological truth is sufficiently general (or generalizable) so it be considered as inter-subjectively accepted and validated.

Regarding the economic logic

I think in the economic (more general, social) field a $4T$ (tetravalent) logic, i.e., a logic with four truth values (face to the Aristotelian two truth values logic – bivalent logic) is adequate and required. The four truth values should be, at the level of descriptive statements, to be compared with the prediction – fact, prescriptive – statements). The four truth values should be (related to the ex ante proposed purpose of the action):

1. A : nominal accomplishment, „with no rest”, of the prescribed purpose, described by a performative statement ($\mathcal{N}_{[p]}$);
2. \bar{A}_+ : nominal missing of the purpose^{vii}, however, accompanied by unintentional^{viii} consequences, convenient to the subject, described by a non-convenient performative statement ($\mathcal{N}_{[p\bar{c}]}$);
3. A_- : nominal accomplishment of the purpose, but accompanied by unintentional consequences, non-convenient to the subject, described by a Convenient, non-performative statement ($\mathcal{N}_{[p\bar{c}]}$);

4. \bar{A} : nominal missing, „with no rest”, of the purpose, described by a non-performative statement ($\mathcal{N}_{[\bar{p}]}$).

Nota bene: in Annex 2 are analytically described the four statements involved in the $4T$ logic.

Regarding the predictors

The issue of predictors is a genuine one within the evolutionary paradigm of the economic process. This, since, in the evolutionary paradigm, the mechanisms of economic, social, and societal evolution are much less accompanied by the incertitude and, as it is well known, the crucial vulnerability of any predictor is the incertitude inherently associated with it. In this regard, I provide the following comments:

- since the mutation in the economic phenotype (an artifact) is either formulated or implemented by the human individual responsible for that phenotype, the transcription and the translation of mutation exactly enter the purpose of the individual in the case (his/her teleology);
- consequently, all the actions subsequently taken in consideration of the mutation are compatible and convergent with that purpose (and, so, with the mutation, either genetic or epigenetic, after the case);
- as a necessary result, any mutation implemented in the economic phenotype has a sufficient degree of certitude regarding its functioning according to the established purpose, so it is very useful predictor within the evolutionary paradigm of economics and economic process.

Regarding the predictions

The specificity of the predictions (predictive statements) within the evolutionary paradigm of economics (and economy) consists exactly in the two elements discussed above: (a) the tetravalent logic; (b) the Lamarckian predictors based on deliberative mutations. Such a way, the predictive statements in this paradigm bear much more certainty than in the alternative paradigms (especially comparative with the neoclassical economic model).

Regarding the testability

The testability within the evolutionary economic theory/model/paradigm is decisively conducted by the specificity of the predictions (and predictors) as they have been described previously. The main features of the (empirical) testability can be synthesized as follows:

- in contrast to the evolutionary phenomenon in the biological case, the prediction in the economic evolutionary model is tested almost exclusively by natural experiments, not by artificial ones;
- as the predictive statement are made on the economic truth, as it has been explained above, i.e., on the human desirability and expectations, not on objective occurrences of the economic process;
- much more than in the natural cases, the testability within the economic evolutionary paradigm is subjected to the precautions indicated by Duhem-Quine thesis.

5. The evolutionary economic paradigm and the smart economy

Basically, a smart economy is an economic system which verify the following sufficiency predicates – the *STA* condition:

- (*S*) is sustainable, i.e., is reproducible through its own principles (forces) on a long-term horizon;
- (*T*) is teleologically conducted, i.e., its finality fits the individual and societal needs;
- (*A*) is autopoietic, i.e., has its own principles to repair, (re)organize, adapt to the environment, and (re)construct the environment itself.

It is easy to observe that the sufficiency predicates of the smart economy are perfectly verified by the above-described model of the evolutionary economic theory or evolutionary paradigm of Economics, as follows:

- i. about predicate (*S*): the requirement of self-reproducing is completely verified by the evolutionary model of evolutionism, since the last include the chreode of phenotype as the result of (fetal) mutation in the genotype or directly (by the epigenetic mutation) on the phenotype. So, the evolutionary paradigm of the economic process objectifies this sufficiency predicate;
- ii. about the predicate (*T*): in the evolutionary model of the economic process (and, correlatively, of the economic theory), all the economic actions/activities are artifacts. This implies that the economic actions/activities are deployed to get a goal consciously pre-established/defined. So, this way of the economic actions/activities leads to conferring the required teleological characteristics of the smart economy, putting the evolutionary economic model in the position of high verifier of the sufficient predicate (*T*) of the smart economy;
- iii. about the predicate (*A*): in the evolutionary paradigm of the economic „world”, any mutation is operated by the human individual, so, a wrong mutation can be corrected by him/her in the next evolutive cycle, according to the purpose of that individual or of the society as a whole. This verifies exactly the sufficiency predicate of the autopoieticity.

Based on the above, we can say that the evolutionary economic paradigm is best positioned to meet the logical requirements of the concept of smart economy.

Annex 1. The general framework of economic theory approaches

There are four strong competitors (challengers) in the matter of reconstruction of economic theory, namely regarding the evolutionary direction of such a reconstruction.

(1) Neoclassical Economics (NE)

- Basic profile: a mechanical model, based on differential equations, in which the individual is considered just an „inert molecule” and where, in fact, causality is basically exogenous
- Impact: directing of the economic/financial theory toward a species of Social Mechanics
- Signification: rejecting of the subject from the economic/financial process (the financial system is considered as a system of order 1, while it is of order 2 and even of order 3)
- Destiny: *NE* exhausted its own possibilities of modelling a real financial world (Colander)

(2) Behavioural Economic (BE)

- Basic profile: a psychological approach, based on adaptation (action-reaction) between system and its environment and, consequently, on learning from experience
- Impact: directing of the economic/financial theory toward a double conditioned theory – from inside: the subject, and from outside: the environment (anthropic and non-anthropoc)
- Signification: re-introduction of the (sensible) subject into the economic process, so that the economic/financial „objects” are considered the result of social construction/re-construction (Berger&Luckmann)
- Destiny: *BE* constitutes one of the basic pillar on which the Evolutionary Model of Finance can and must be anchored

(3) Economics of Fractality (EF)

- Basic profile: a topological (both spatial and temporal) pattern of distributing of opportunities, risks, returns and other economic/financial variables, based on fractal dimension (or fractal dimensioning as such) (Peters, 1994)
- Impact: introduction of a new (plausible) logic in economic decision-making and economic action, in which both objective and subjective factors are inherently entangled
- Signification: replacing the un-realistic de *Moivre-Gauss* distribution (of cardinal or ordinal values) in economy/finance with a more realist fractal distribution

- Destiny: to be combined, logically, psychologically, and methodologically, with the Behavioural Economics, so accounting for an Evolutionary Model of Finance (EMF)

(4) *Economics of Chaos (EC)*

- Basic profile: a dynamic theorizing/modelling of the economic/financial phenomenon, based on the high sensitivity of the behaviour (as decision and act) related to the initial conditions – which is closer to the psychologic matrix of the human being
- Impact: introducing of attractors vs. sources points in economic/financial kinematics
- Signification: eliminating the objective (frequential) probabilities of Kolmogorov type from economic/financial modelling (*Nota bene*: although the Bayesian probabilities could survive if concomitantly aligned to BE and FE)
- Destiny: besides BE and FE, EC, EC completes the three pillars of EMF (*Nota bene*: as known, at most three points of support deliver a single stable plan, namely EMF).

Annex 2. The statements in the 4 \mathcal{T} logic

- *performative statement* ($\mathcal{N}_{[p]}$). The value of occurrence of this prescriptive statement is noted with A . A performative statement signifies that the purpose prescribed within has been accomplished through the action associated to that purpose. Furthermore, this statement „specifies” that no unintended consequences^{ix} appeared while accomplishing the purpose, therefore this was done „with no rest”. Purely analogically, this type of statements corresponds to the type of true statements from the bivalent logics;
- *convenient, non-performative statement* ($\mathcal{N}_{[p\bar{c}]}$). The value of occurrence of this prescriptive statement is noted with \bar{A}_+ . A convenient, non-performative statement signifies (by the term *non-performative*) that the prescribed purpose has not been accomplished; however, some consequences unintended by the normative subject were produced, which are convenient to the evaluating subject (by the term *convenient*). We have two things to notice here: a) the unintended consequences must also be convenient for the normative subject, because the attribute of *convenient* also bears on the prescriptive statement, which has been formulated by the normative subject; b) the unintended convenient consequences don't mean a partial accomplishment of the purpose, but they merely, and unavoidably accompany the unfulfillment of the purpose. The suggestion of benefit associated to a failure cannot be circumvented here^x. Purely analogically, this type of statements corresponds to the types of statements from the bivalent logics;
- *non-convenient performative statement* ($\mathcal{N}_{[p\bar{c}]}$). The value of occurrence of this prescriptive statement a is noted with A_- . A non-convenient performative statement signifies (by the term *performative*), that the prescribed purpose has been accomplished and that consequences unintended by the normative subject were produced during the process, and are non-convenient to the evaluating subject (shown by the term *non-convenient*). Same as before, there are two things to notice: a) the unintended consequences must be non-convenient to the normative subject too, because the attribute of *non-convenient* bears on the prescriptive statement formulated by the normative subject; b) the unintended non-convenient consequences don't mean a partial failure of the purpose, but they merely, and unavoidably accompany the accomplishment of the purpose. The suggestion of transaction cost associated to a performance cannot be circumvented here^{xi}. Purely analogically, this type of statements has no correspondent in the types of statements from the bivalent logics;
- *non-performative statement* ($\mathcal{N}_{[\bar{p}]}$). The value of occurrence of this prescriptive statement is noted with \bar{A} . A non-performative statement signifies that the prescribed purpose has not been accomplished through the action associated to that purpose. Furthermore, this statement „specifies” that no unintended consequences appeared while trying to accomplish that purpose, therefore this was done „with no rest”. Purely analogically, this type of statements corresponds to the type of false statements from the bivalent logics.

Conflicts of Interest

The author declares that there are no conflicts of interest regarding the publication of this paper.

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ⁱ In my opinion, the institutionalism is a species of evolutionism (Dinga, 2021)

ⁱⁱ Here, the expression *efficient cause* is used in the Aristotelian meaning.

ⁱⁱⁱ The economic time and space are not influenced (in terms of the economic speed, acceleration, density, “bending”) by the properties of the economic process they measure.

^{iv} Or final conditions; it is readily observable that logically, the initial conditions are equivalent with the final conditions.

^v Let us notice that the same thing appears in the quantum mechanics too, in the area of phases.

^{vi} As known, the truth, especially the scientific one, is characterized by the fact that it is established by consensus (or, in the worst case, by the majority of the „voters”, i.e., by the community’s members, generally adopting the same cognitive paradigm).

^{vii} The negation sign (\bar{A}) has the same significance as in the classical logics, which allows formulating the principle of identity ($A = A$), the principle of non-contradiction ($\overline{A \wedge \bar{A}}$), and the principle of the excluded third ($A \vee \bar{A}$).

^{viii} The concept of unintended consequence has been highly theorized by Karl Popper, who was saying that the most important task of the social sciences is to make predictions about the unintended consequences of the taken decisions.

^{ix} The problem of evaluating the unintended consequences while accomplishing a purpose is not too simple. Logically, the assessment of the appearance or not of consequences beyond the purpose cannot be done unless there is a benchmark. But the prescriptive statement expresses no such consequences. Would they have been expressed, they would no longer be unintended, thus being part of the purpose. We revert thus to the initial problem, not having a benchmark to evaluate the unintended consequences. The situation „worsens” further when praxeologically, $NS_{-1} \neq ES_1$.

^x This is an idea to be developed subsequently, because it seems to us that it has a great explanative potential for the process of evaluating the human action in general.

^{xi} The concept of cost of transaction is well known to the economists: that cost (not necessarily monetary) which accompanies any transaction (here, the term of transaction is taken in its most general meaning, of voluntary, inter-subjects, interaction), and it adds to the price of the transaction. Therefore, we have a price of transaction (p_t), we have a cost of transaction (c_t) and we have a transactional price (p^T), so that: $p^T = p_t + c_t$. *Nota bene*: c_t must be recalculated in units equivalent with those used to measure p_t (for instance, in monetary units).